

OPTIMUM BUCKLING LOAD OF HETEROGENEOUS COMPOSITE PLATES SUBJECTED TO UNCERTAIN THERMAL AND MECHANICAL LOADINGS

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SUMMARY: Optimization of heterogeneous composite aerospace structures that operate in a range of temperatures is considered in this paper. It is observed that heterogeneous composite plates optimized to operate at a fixed service temperature may perform poorly when that temperature is varied, i.e., those plates may be highly sensitive to thermal loadings. A strategy is presented to obtain optimal designs of heterogeneous composite plates that operate within a given temperature range and under arbitrary mechanical loading such that the significant and undesired sensitivity of these optimal designs to both thermal and mechanical loadings are effectively suppressed. It is assumed that the mechanical loading distribution is arbitrarily piecewise linear and the operating temperature is within a specified range. Hence, the applied loadings are uncertain or not fixed in nature. Results for heterogeneous composite plates demonstrate the effectiveness of the strategy proposed and the danger of utilizing composite designs sensitive to variations in the thermal and mechanical loadings.

KEYWORDS: uncertain loadings, structural optimization, thermal residual stresses.

INTRODUCTION

A number of investigations have been conducted in the past addressing buckling optimization of composite structures. A common feature of these optimization studies is that, in most of them, the applied in-plane loading distribution is uniform and the service temperature of the structural component is constant. Thus, the buckling load magnitude is the objective function to be maximized.

Specification of both mechanical loading distribution and operation temperature may result in optimal designs that present significant sensitivity to variations in the loading configuration. The optimization problem of an isotropic plate with piecewise constant thickness subjected to an arbitrary nonuniform loading distribution was considered in Ref. [1]. The loading distribution was modeled as a piecewise linear function and it was assumed that the prebuckling behavior is temperature independent. However, heterogeneous composite plates are not free of thermal residual stresses inherited from the cure processing at elevated temperatures [2]. The effect of these thermal residual stresses on buckling loads may be quite significant and depends on the difference between service and cure temperature. It is important to remark that a composite plate optimized to operate at a specified fixed temperature may perform poorly at another temperature. Therefore, considering that

aerospace structures actually operate within reasonably wide temperature ranges, the design may be vulnerable to temperature variations within the operating range.

The fundamental idea of this work is to propose an optimization procedure that accounts for variations of both mechanical and thermal loadings within given bounds. It is assumed that the mechanical loading distribution is arbitrarily piecewise linear [1] and the operating temperature is within a specified range. Therefore, the mechanical and thermal loading distributions are uncertain or not fixed. A detailed explanation of the technique to treat uncertain loads is not the focus of this paper but its rigorous proof [3] and application to buckling optimization problems is well documented [1,4].

PROBLEM FORMULATION

The design variables of the optimization problem considered are the thicknesses of the composite plate that vary from region to region, the mechanical loading distributions that vary continuously and the thermal residual stress distribution while the objective function is the critical buckling load. Figure 1a illustrates an arbitrary piecewise linear loading distribution in a 3D view of a composite plate with variable thickness where the thicknesses are exaggerated to facilitate visualization.

The strips in Fig. 1a represent regions with different thicknesses. Those regions are referred to as reinforcements due to their discrete nature. A base plate is defined such that the plate thickness at any point cannot be smaller than the thickness of the base plate. The base plate is chosen to be a $[0/90]_S$ laminate; its total thickness is kept constant and its four layers have equal thicknesses. On the other hand, the outermost layers have variable thicknesses that must be assigned observing laminate symmetry. The stacking sequence can be better visualized in Fig. 1b where an arbitrary cross-section of the plate is shown with ply orientations. It can be inferred that the stacking sequence of reinforcement i is represented by $[0^{h_{2i}}/90^{h_{2i-1}}/0^{\bar{h}/4}/90^{\bar{h}/4}]_S$ where \bar{h} is the base plate thickness, h_{2i-1} is thickness of the outer 90° ply and h_{2i} is thickness of the outer 0° ply.

Fig. 1: Symmetric composite plate

The optimization problem must be formulated as to take into account the variability of the piecewise linear loading distribution shown in Fig. 1a as well as the variable service temperature. This can be done via a minimax formulation as given in Eq. (1) [1]:

$$\max_{\mathbf{h}} \min_{\mathbf{r}, \Delta T} \mathbf{I}(\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{r}, \Delta T) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{h} is the vector of reinforcement thicknesses, $\mathbf{r} = (R_1, \dots, R_m)$ is the vector of uncertain loads when m loading components are considered, ΔT is the difference between the service and cure temperatures and \mathbf{I} is the buckling load magnitude, i.e., the objective function of the problem. The definition of \mathbf{r} and the physical significance of its components R_i can be found in Ref. 1 but it is worth mentioning that the components R_i hold the following relationship: $\sum R_i = 1$ and $R_i \in [0,1]$. The arbitrary piecewise loading distribution is represented through a series of piecewise linear basis functions defined at specific points along the plate edges. Component R_i is associated with the i th basis function and provides a measure of its relative contribution to the overall piecewise linear loading while the basis functions themselves define the shape of the loading distribution. The composite plates optimized have constant volume such that a constraint to the optimization problem exists: summation of the outermost ply thicknesses shown in Fig. 1b must be constant.

Solution of the problem stated in Eq. (1) provides, simultaneously, the optimal design and the worst loading combination in terms of \mathbf{r} and ΔT . The considered optimization problem is bilevel and its numerical solution is often laborious. However, the fact that \mathbf{I} is obtained through solution of the classic eigenvalue problem allows for a tremendous simplification if the extended stability boundary theorem [3] is used.

Calculation of the objective function \mathbf{I} is divided into three steps: (i) solution of a linear thermal problem to obtain thermal residual stresses, (ii) solution of a linear prebuckling problem to obtain prebuckling mechanical stresses and (iii) solution of an eigenvalue problem to obtain the buckling load. Furthermore, the laminate is symmetric and assumed free of initial imperfections such that a bifurcation type of buckling is observed. The resulting thermal, prebuckling and buckling problems can be stated, respectively, in a compact form as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K}\mathbf{q}_t &= \mathbf{f}_t \\ \mathbf{K}\mathbf{q}_p &= \mathbf{f}_p \\ (\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_t - \mathbf{I}\mathbf{K}_G)\mathbf{q} &= \mathbf{0} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The thermal load vector \mathbf{f}_t is proportional to the difference ΔT between operation and processing temperatures. Accordingly, the thermal geometric stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_t is also proportional to ΔT . For example, assuming a cure temperature of 120°C and operation temperature of 25°C, both \mathbf{f}_t and \mathbf{K}_t are proportional to $\Delta T = -95^\circ\text{C}$.

The stability boundary theorem is valid provided $\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_t$ is positive-definite and even when \mathbf{K}_G is indefinite [3]. Matrix $\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_t$ is guaranteed to be positive-definite if thermal buckling has not occurred. Since buckling maximization is sought the optimizer will avoid designs that result in matrices \mathbf{K}_t that render $\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_t$ indefinite ensuring that the hypothesis of the stability boundary theorem is observed. However, as a safe guard, a Sturm check of $\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_t$ is conducted for every design evaluated to make sure that positive-definiteness is satisfied. This check adds little computational cost to the analysis because matrix $\mathbf{K} + \mathbf{K}_t$ must be decomposed anyway in order to obtain the eigenvalues of the problem in Eq. (2c).

Minimization of $I(\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{r}, \Delta T)$ with respect to \mathbf{r} and ΔT is easily accomplished with the aid of the stability boundary theorem because it suffices to evaluate I at extremal points. Assuming that the service temperature can vary within a range $\Delta T_{\min} \leq \Delta T \leq \Delta T_{\max}$ these extremal points correspond to $R_i = 1$ and $\Delta T = \Delta T_{\min}$, and $R_i = 1$ and $\Delta T = \Delta T_{\max}$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$, i.e., there are $2m$ extremal points.

The solution of the optimization problem is initiated by assessing 400 random designs in an attempt to reduce the risk of convergence to local optima. The best design obtained by the random procedure is taken as the starting point for a Powell's search[5]. The eigenvalues of the problem may be non-smooth but they are certainly continuous. Hence, an optimization algorithm that requires only C^0 continuity of the objective function and constraints was selected (Powell's method). Alternative strategies can be employed to handle the non-smoothness of the eigenvalues such that more efficient gradient-based optimization methods can be used to ensure faster convergence to the optimal design [6]. The optimization stops when the relative difference between the previous and present values of \mathbf{f} does not exceed 0.001, where \mathbf{f} is the minimum I over the admissible loading configurations \mathbf{r} and temperature difference ΔT . In other words, \mathbf{f} is the solution of the inner loop of the minimax problem stated in Eq. (1).

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS AND DISCUSSION

A square plate simply supported along four edges with sides of 360 mm is investigated where the loading is applied along the sides parallel to the y axis as shown in Fig. 1a. The material chosen for simulation is graphite/epoxy T300-5208 whose properties are given in Table 1. Four reinforcements are considered and five piecewise linear basis functions are defined at positions $y = 0, 90, 180, 270$ and 360 mm along the two opposite edges parallel to the y axis. The base plate total thickness is 0.3 mm such that each base ply is 0.075 mm thick. Moreover, a constant volume constraint is imposed such that $\Sigma(h_{2i-1} + h_{2i}) = 0.6$ mm, $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. The processing temperature adopted is 120°C and the service temperature ranges from -60°C and $+40^\circ\text{C}$ such that $-180^\circ\text{C} \leq \Delta T \leq -80^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 1: Material properties of the T300-5208 graphite/epoxy

property	value
Principal modulus of elasticity, E_{11}	154.0 GPa
Principal modulus of elasticity, E_{22}	11.13 GPa
In-plane Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.304
In-plane shear modulus, G_{12}	6.98 GPa
Transverse shear modulus, G_{13}	6.98 GPa
Transverse shear modulus, G_{23}	3.36 GPa
Principal thermal expansion coefficient, α_1	$-0.17 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
Principal thermal expansion coefficient, α_2	$23.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$

Initially, it would be interesting to establish a comparison between the optimal designs obtained under traditional assumptions and the present strategy. For that purpose it is worth finding a few classical optimal designs for fixed loading distributions and fixed operation temperature of 20°C , for instance, such that $\Delta T = -100^\circ\text{C}$. Figures 2a-c depict sketches of the optimal plate configurations obtained when individual distributed loading components (basis functions) are applied and Fig 2d presents the optimal plate for the uniform loading. The force magnitudes are the optimal net forces caused by the distributed loadings whose shapes are also shown. Because of the symmetry of the basis functions about $y = 180 \text{ mm}$, only three cases are shown.

Fig. 2: Classic optimal designs and loads

Notice that the optimal design obtained for $R_3 = 1.0$ (Fig. 2c) is slightly nonsymmetric with respect to the plate center line $y = 180$ mm despite the fact that the loading and boundary conditions are. This is in accordance with the optimal design that would have been obtained if the material considered were isotropic since, in this case, a pronounced nonsymmetric design is reached [1]. On the other hand, when the uniform loading is applied (Fig. 2d), the optimal design found is perfectly symmetric. This observation justifies the use of full meshes to model the entire plate without previously assuming any kind of symmetry for the optimal designs.

Table 2 presents results concerning sensitivity of the optimal designs obtained for variations in the mechanical loadings. The lines of Table 2 correspond to the optimal designs presented in Figs. 2a-d and columns correspond to the loading distribution components applied at a constant temperature difference $\Delta T = -100^\circ\text{C}$. It can be observed that all optimal designs perform poorly if the loading configuration applied is other than that particular one for which it was optimized. For instance, the optimal design of Fig. 2a may have its critical load dramatically reduced if an unfavorable loading distribution is applied. The conclusion drawn is that the thermal residual stresses in the optimal design of Fig. 2a lead to potentially unstable plates since very small forces applied at unfavorable locations imply loss of stability. This is obviously a very dangerous design and would not be a good choice in practical situations.

Table 2: Mechanical sensitivity of traditional optimal designs

optimal design	$R_1 = 1$	$R_2 = 1$	$R_3 = 1$	$R_4 = 1$	$R_5 = 1$	uniform
1 (Fig 2a)	895.2 N	235.8 N	2.7 N	1.5 N	2.8 N	3.2 N
2 (Fig 2b)	729.4 N	284.4 N	39.8 N	11.6 N	11.6 N	26.2 N
3 (Fig 2c)	69.3 N	66.0 N	171.9 N	93.6 N	98.4 N	149.0 N
4 (Fig 2d)	174.7 N	142.3 N	139.6 N	142.3 N	174.7 N	270.2 N

Figure 3 presents the sensitivity of the obtained optimal designs to variations in the thermal loads. The mechanical loading distribution is maintained constant as in the optimal designs presented in Figs. 2a-d and the temperature difference ΔT is varied from 0°C until the point where thermal buckling is observed. High sensitivities to temperature variations are noticed for the optimal designs. The sensitivity is particularly high near $\Delta T = -100^\circ\text{C}$ because the plates were optimized to operate at this temperature using the traditional approach. As expected, the maximum buckling loads for all plates correspond to ΔT approximately equal to -100°C . In the case of the optimal design related to Fig. 2a thermal buckling happens when $\Delta T = -105.1^\circ\text{C}$ whereas for Fig. 2b it occurs when $\Delta T = -127.2^\circ\text{C}$, both within the plate operating temperature range. The results shown in Fig. 3 clearly demonstrate the danger of optimal designs obtained under fixed thermal loads assumptions

Fig. 3: Thermal sensitivity of traditional optimal designs

Figure 4 shows the optimal plate obtained by the minimax strategy. In this case the critical buckling loads are shown in Table 3 for all different loading configurations. The buckling loads are now much less sensitive to loading distribution than those presented in Table 2 and with the corresponding configurations illustrated in Figs 2a-c. For the minimax optimal design presented in Fig. 4 the critical load I is greater than 126.0 N for any loading combination \mathbf{r} and ΔT provided that $\sum R_i = 1$, $R_i \geq 0$ and $-180^\circ\text{C} \leq \Delta T \leq -80^\circ\text{C}$. Direct comparison of the minimax optimal design (Fig. 4) and the optimal design shown in Fig. 2d may be misleading because, apparently, the later has better performance over the former by simple observation of Tables 2 and 3. This is not true since buckling at different temperatures must also be assessed in order to make a fair comparison. In this sense, when $R_2 = 1$ and $\Delta T = -180^\circ\text{C}$, the optimal design of Fig. 2d leads to $I = 72.2$ N, well below 126.0 N.

Table 3: Minimax optimal design: buckling loads

	$R_1 = 1$	$R_2 = 1$	$R_3 = 1$	$R_4 = 1$	$R_5 = 1$	uniform
$\Delta T = -180^\circ\text{C}$	139.8 N	127.2 N	161.3 N	127.2 N	139.8 N	262.4 N
$\Delta T = -80^\circ\text{C}$	210.9 N	146.5 N	126.0 N	146.5 N	210.9 N	233.3 N

Fig. 4: Optimal design subjected to uncertain loads

A finite element mesh of 8×8 elements was used throughout. Refinement of the plate FE mesh does not significantly alter results since the element used is bicubic Lagrangian [2] whose complexity (the element has 80 degrees of freedom) allows for the use of relatively coarse FE meshes. Finer meshes (12×12) have been tried with small variation in terms of buckling loads (less than 5%) and they certainly improve accuracy but also require more computer processing what is costly since an optimization is done and, therefore, computation of eigenvalues is performed thousands of times.

CONCLUSIONS

Buckling optimization of composite plates subjected to piecewise linear loadings is resolved within the scope of a minimax strategy. The thermal residual stresses that are inherited from the thermal processing are included in the analysis. As a matter of fact, the optimization procedure obtains optimal designs that take advantage of the thermal residual stresses. If disregarded those residual stresses will probably impair the performance of composite plates [2].

Traditionally, aerospace structural components optimized for buckling are ideally subjected to perfectly uniform compressive loads and thermal effects are ignored. However, this mechanical loading configuration is rarely observed in actual service conditions and thermal effects may strongly affect the performance of composite plates. Therefore, this procedure may result in designs that are not optimal and that may be highly sensitive to variations in the applied loading and temperature. This paper proposes a reformulation of the problem in order to accommodate the uncertain nature of the mechanical and thermal loadings.

The simple examples investigated demonstrate the danger of high sensitivity to mechanical and thermal loading perturbations by optimizing composite plates with piecewise constant thickness. It was determined that the worst loading acting on the minimax optimal composite plate in Fig. 4 is the one where $R_3 = 1$ and $\Delta T = -80^\circ\text{C}$ (or $R_2 = 1$ and $\Delta T = -180^\circ\text{C}$) with the associated buckling load $I = 126.0 \text{ N}$. The optimization problem is posed such as to guarantee that, if the mechanical loading configuration and/or the service temperature are changed within the admissible set, the buckling load will not decrease, i.e., $I > 126.0 \text{ N}$.

The uncertainty of the loading is assumed to be associated with one direction (the x axis). Consideration of uncertain loadings acting in the y axis of the plate is straightforward because all one must do is to include the applicable proportionality parameters R_i 's in vector \mathbf{r} and enforce the convex combination constraint $\sum R_i = 1$. In this situation it may be more effective to assume that the plate thickness varies in both x and y directions.

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